

New Synthetic Routes to Isothioammelides, Isothioammelins and their Thioethers. Part II. Interaction of Carbondisulphide with S-Benzylamidinoisothiocarbamides

J. D. DHAKE

University Department of Chemistry and Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur University, Nagpur

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In continuation to the earlier work,^{1,2} interaction of 1-*p*-tolyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino-S-benzylisothiocarbamide and unsubstituted amidinothiocarbamide with carbon disulphide and appropriate followup treatment have been shown to result in the related cyclic products the thiadiazines, thioammelides, thioammelins and their thioethers. Structures of all the thioammelides as also of some of the other products have been confirmed by their independent synthesis.

INTERACTION of carbon disulphide with S-benzylamidinoisothiocarbamides (I) is expected to afford the corresponding dithiocarbamic acid derivatives (II) but the product isolated in the case of Ia and Ib have been shown^{1,2} to be the related cyclic products, the thiadiazine derivative (III)a and (III)b.

and the identity of the synthetic products with those obtained from the reaction have been confirmed through their undepressed m.m.p. and superimposable IR spectra.

All the compounds of the series Id to VIId have also been synthesised by alternate routes known earlier

- wherein (a) R = R' = methyl and X = benzyl
 (b) R = H and R' = *p*-tolyl and X = benzyl
 (c) R = R' = *p*-tolyl and X = benzyl
 (d) R = R' = H and X = H.

Although the thiadiazines (III) are stable to acids and mild basic solvents like ethanol and even dimethylformamide, on exposure to strongly alkaline conditions these rearrange into the related 1,3,5-triazine derivatives, the thioammelides (IV). The latter on reaction with amines and alkyl halides form the corresponding thioammelins (VI) and thioethers (V).

and their identity established by the usual techniques.

Experimental

Preparation of S-benzyl-1-*p*-tolyl-3-*p*-tolylamidinoisothiocarbamide

All these reactions have now been shown to take place also with Ic and Id affording the products corresponding to IIIa and IIIc through VIa and VIc. The reaction sequence thus appears to be of general applicability.

The required 1-*p*-tolyl-3-*p*-tolylamidinothiocarbamide³ was prepared by the interaction of *p*-tolylisothiocyanate and *p*-tolylguanidine carbonate. On reaction with benzyl chloride in a refluxing ethanolic medium for one hour it afforded a crystalline hydrochloride identified as that of the related S-benzylisothiocarbamide; recrystallised from ethanol, m.p.

The isodithioammelides IVa and IVc have also been synthesised by the following independent route

R & R' as above; Bz = benzyl; R'' = benzyl.

180°. Molar equivalent: Found 415; $C_{23}H_{24}N_4S$, HCl requires 424.5. On basification of hydrochloride with aq. ammonia, the related free base was precipitated; crystals from ethanol, m.p. 125°. Found: C, 71.14; H, 6.71; N, 14.78; S, 8.67; $C_{23}H_{24}N_4S$ requires: C, 71.14; H, 6.22; N, 14.43; S, 8.24%.

Interaction of Ic with carbon disulphide in benzene leading to thiadiazine IIIc:

When a solution of S-benzyl-1-p-tolyl-3-p-tolyl-amidinoisothiocarbamide (Ic) in benzene (3 g in 60 ml) was mixed with carbon disulphide (10 ml) and the mixture heated on waterbath under a reflux condenser for 3.5 hr, benzyl mercaptan and traces of hydrogen sulphide were found to be evolved and a pale yellow product separated (0.6 g) on filtration and washing with acetone, m.p. 230°. When to the

where R & R' are as above.

filtrate a fresh quantity of carbon disulphide (5 ml) was added and heating resumed, after about 2 hr, a second crop (0.3 g) of the same product separated and was filtered out. This procedure was repeated till no more solid separated; total yield 1.2 g. It could not be crystallised satisfactorily from ethanol or other solvents and was purified by washing it repeatedly with acetone and finally by boiling with ethanol to remove any alcohol soluble impurities. Found: C, 60.64; H, 5.20; N, 16.13; S, 19.05; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4S_2$ requires C, 60.00; H, 4.7; N, 16.47 and S, 18.80%. Its IR spectrum showed the following bands (cm^{-1}) and it has been assigned structure IIIc. 3200 m, NH stretching, (Lit.⁸, 3400-3100); 1600 m, C = N (Lit.^{10a}, 1685-1582); 1216 s, -C-NH (Lit.^{10c}, 1400-700).

Interaction of IIIc with ethanolic alkali: Formation of the potassium salt of IVc:

The thiazine IIIc (0.5 g) was dissolved in ethanolic alkali (20 ml) and the solution heated under reflux for 30 min. and filtered. The clear filtrate on cooling deposited colourless crystals, on recrystallisation from hot water, m.p. 284°. Its aqueous solution on acidification afforded the triazine IVc, m.p. 260°. The IVc on treatment with ethanolic potassium hydroxide reprecipitated the dipotassium salt, m.p. 284°. Found: S, 15.81; N, 13.39; $C_{17}H_{14}N_4S_2K_2$ requires S, 15.38; N, 13.46%. Its IR spectrum showed the following bands (cm^{-1}): 3200 w, NH stretching, (Lit.⁸, 3400-3100); 1550 s, 1,3,5-triazine (Lit.^{9b}, 1550); 1590 w, C = N (Lit.^{9a}, 1685-1582); 785, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{9a}, 795-750).

The triazine base IVc, m.p. 260° obtained by the acidification of its dipotassium salt was purified again by dissolving in ethanolic alkali and reprecipitation by acid. Found: S, 18.3; N, 16.2; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4S_2$ requires S, 18.8; N, 16.5%. Its IR spectrum showed the following bands (cm^{-1}): 3150 w, NH stretching (Lit.⁸, 3400-3100); 1570 s, shoulder, 1,3,5-triazine (Lit.^{9b}, 1550); 1610 s, shoulder C = N (Lit.^{9a}, 1685-1582); 1210 HN-C- (Lit.^{9c}, 1400-700); N-C-N (Lit.^{9e}, 1200); 775 s, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{9d}, 795-750).

Interaction of benzyl chloride with the thiadiazine IIIc leading to the thioether Vc:

A mixture of IIIc (0.5 g), ethanol (25 ml) and benzyl chloride (1 ml) was heated under gentle reflux for 2 hr. The solution was filtered and the clear acidic filtrate allowed to stand when a solid separated which crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 305° (d). Molar equivalent: Found 478; $C_{24}H_{22}N_4S_2$, HCl requires 466.5. It was identified as the hydrochloride of Vc (vide *infra*).

Interaction of benzyl chloride with IVc leading to Vc:

A mixture of the triazine IVc (1 g), ethanol (30 ml) and benzyl chloride (1 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 hr. On filtration and cooling a colourless solid acidic to litmus was obtained, m.p. 305° (d). Molar equivalent: Found 469; $C_{24}H_{22}N_4S_2$, HCl requires

466-5. Found : S, 13.4; N, 12.4; $C_{24}H_{22}N_4S_2$, HCl requires S, 13.8; N, 12.0%. On basification with ammonia, the related free base Vc was obtained, crystals from aq. ethanol, m.p. 245°. Found : N, 12.7; $C_{24}H_{22}N_4S_2$ requires N, 13.0%.

Interaction of IIIc with benzylamine leading to VIc :

A mixture of IIIc (1 g) and benzylamine (2 ml) was heated at 180° for 1-hr. when H_2S was found to be evolved. The resultant liquid on pouring in cold dil. hydrochloric acid afforded a sticky solid; on washing with petroleum ether and crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 120°. Found : N, 16.41; $C_{24}H_{23}N_5S$ requires N, 16.94%. It gave no depression in m.p. when mixed with the product obtained by the interaction of benzylamine with Vc under similar conditions. It is evident that the product must have arisen through the intermediate formation of IVc. Its IR spectrum showed the following bands (cm^{-1}) : 3210 m, NH stretching, (Lit. , 3400-3100); 1550 s, 1,3,5-triazine (Lit.^{9b}, 1550); 1216 s, N-C-N- (Lit.^{9c}, 1200); 745 vs, 770 w, "iso" form

of triazine ring (Lit.^{9d}, 795-750).

Interaction of Vc with benzylamine : Formation of VIc :

A mixture of Vc (0.5 g), benzylamine (1 ml) and a little ethanol was heated under reflux for 4 hr. During the reaction smell of benzylmercaptan was perceptible. The resultant liquid on pouring in cold dil. hydrochloric acid afforded a solid on crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 120°. It gave no depression in m.m.p. with the product obtained in the expt. no. 6. Found : S, 7.4; N, 16.6; $C_{24}H_{23}N_5S$ requires S, 7.9; N, 16.9%.

Synthesis of IVc from VIIc and p-toluidine :

When a mixture of VIIc, p-toluidine and methanol was heated under gentle reflux for 4 hr, H_2S was eliminated and a pale yellow solid separated out. It was purified by dissolving it in ethanolic alkali and reprecipitating with hydrochloric acid, m.p. 260°. Found : S, 18.6; N, 16.8; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4S_2$ requires S, 18.8 and N, 16.6%. It was found to be identical with the product (IVc) obtained by the isomeric change of IIIc (m.m.p. and IR).

Interaction of Id with carbon disulphide : Formation of IIIId :

The required amidinothiocarbamide (Id) was prepared by Kurzer's method⁴. A mixture of Id (4 g), dimethylformamide (20 ml) and carbon disulphide (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 12 hr. H_2S was liberated during the reaction. On cooling the heavier layer of CS_2 was removed and the upper layer was evaporated when a yellow solid was obtained. It was washed with ether followed by small quantity of water, m.p. 300°. Crystals from hot

water, m.p. 300°. Found : S, 39.4; N, 34.8; $C_3H_4N_4S_2$ requires S, 40.0; N, 35.0%. Its identification as 2,4-dimino-6-thio-1,3,5-thiadiazine (IIIId) was confirmed by ethylating it with ethyl iodide when the hydroiodide of 2-mercaptoethyl-4-imino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazine (m.p. 195°) was obtained, m.m.p. with the authentic sample of the thioether Vd 195° (m.p. lit.⁵ 195°).

Interaction of IIIId with alkali leading to IVd :

A solution of IIIId (0.5 g) in 10 ml of 1N NaOH was heated on a boiling water bath for 30 min. The resulting yellow solution on acidification with acetic acid afforded a colourless, granular solid. It was crystallised from hot water, m.p. 300°. Found : S, 40.3; N, 34.6; $C_3H_4N_4S_2$ requires S, 40.0; N, 35.0%. It was identified as 2,4-dithio-6-imino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine⁶ (IVd), m.p. 300°. On ethylating it afforded the hydroiodide of an ethylthioether, m.p. 195°⁷. Molar equivalent found acidimetrically, 155.4; $C_5H_9N_4S_2$, HI requires 317 (158.5 as half value). Found : S, 19.8; N, 17.4; $C_5H_9N_4S_2$, HI requires S, 20.25; N, 17.7%. It gave no depression in m.m.p. with the product m.p. 195° obtained by the ethylation of an authentic sample⁸ of IVd.

Interaction of Vd (where there is an ethyl group in place of benzyl) with aniline leading to thioammeline (VIId) :

A mixture of 2-thio-4-S-ethyl-6-imino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine hydroiodide (0.5 g), aniline (1 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) was shaken at room temp. for a few minutes when a colourless solid separated, m.p. 278°. Crystallised from water, m.p. 280°. Found : N, 31.4; $C_9H_9N_5S$ requires N, 31.96%. This was 2-thio-4-anilino-6-imino-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine (Vd where R" = Ph). It gave no depression in m.m.p. with an authentic sample (m.p. 280°)⁷.

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